

RECOMMENDATIONS FROM ODECO: ADVANCING VALUE CREATION FROM OPEN GOVERNMENT DATA IN THE NETHERLANDS

Position Paper
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Open government data (OGD) holds the promise of empowering individuals and organisations by treating data as a shared societal asset. However, *key challenges remain*: data is often **underutilised**, and **social value is lacking**. Despite an increase in open government data availability, reuse, and value creation lag behind. This is partly due to a **mismatch** between what data governments provide and what stakeholders actually need. Current EU policies often frame open data primarily as an economic resource, increasing the tension between a vision of OGD as a societal good and the privatisation of gains deriving from its exploitation.

This policy paper distils a set of governance strategies developed in the context of the research conducted by the **ODECO** project. It addresses concerns over the lack of inclusiveness and equity of OGD, which results in the unsatisfactory delivery of social value. We propose a two-step approach. First, we present strategies to implement in the short term to elicit the reuse of data and align it with the concept of societal values. These **Action Principles** include:

1. **Support Communities of Shared Purpose and Practice:** Promote communities focused on shared goals (e.g., civic engagement) and expertise (e.g., data practitioners) to encourage meaningful OGD use.
2. **Encourage Polycentric Governance:** Ensure that less powerful actors, such as citizens and small NGOs, are actively included in decision-making processes through both institutional and collaborative mechanisms.
3. **Ensure Public Funding for Economic Sustainability:** Ensure adequate public investment in data infrastructure and promote strategies for financial sustainability within the OGD ecosystem.

Second, we look at the **structural issues** that impede or limit the delivery of equitable governance of OGD. The Action Principles cannot solve the power imbalances that the view of open data as an economic asset creates. Thus, we present a set of **Governance Solutions**:

- **Purpose-Driven Data Initiatives:** Align data release and reuse with societal goals like climate action, healthcare, and community development.
- **Governance Reform:** Adopt decentralised and participatory governance models to enhance transparency and accountability and address power imbalances.
- **Capacity Building:** Provide technical, financial, and infrastructure-related resources and support to empower smaller and under-resourced stakeholders.
- **Innovative Incentives and Regulations:** Use tools such as tax breaks, subsidies or public-private partnerships to incentivise inclusive participation and equitable benefits redistribution.

By rethinking how value is created and can be better distributed, and by centering governance on **equity**, OGD can fulfil its potential as a *shared societal asset* for economic and social value generation.

This policy paper presents *key insights* and *practical recommendations* from four years of research conducted by the ODECO (*Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem*) project, a Marie Curie initiative involving researchers across European universities and institutions, in partnership with public and private sector partners. Through interdisciplinary research and real-world case studies, we have identified practical recommendations to tackle **the lack of open data utilisation** and subsequent **lack of value creation**. Our set of recommendations is based on ODECO's Deliverables 2.3 and 5.2. It supports the building of a more *sustainable, equitable, and effective open (government) data ecosystem*.

GOING BEYOND ECONOMIC VALUE

Open Government Data (OGD) holds the promise of being a *shared societal asset*, creating economic and social value, increasing transparency and citizens' participation. OGD is not a finite resource, so its value should increase with each instance of reuse [i]. Despite the efforts to engage a variety of users, key challenges remain: **data underutilisation** and **lack of social value**. The increased volumes of OGD do not translate into a reuse rate and value creation. One of the reasons is a *mismatch* between shared governmental datasets and what is of relevance for the stakeholders.

Various policy and regulatory measures introduced by the European Commission emphasise **only economic aspects** of OGD value, characterising it as an economic resource and as a factor in boosting innovation in the digital economy [ii]. This narrow framing reinforces the mismatch, overlooking the broader societal value of open data and limiting its full potential.

To solve these challenges, we propose focusing on the set of Action Principles, informed by principles of co-creation. In this way, value is not created in isolation but arises through the collaborative efforts of multiple stakeholders. This co-creation process helps shape value propositions that **reflect collective needs**, with value shared across stakeholders, including businesses, governments, and citizens [iii]. To achieve an ecosystem where these processes are possible requires that governance extends beyond technical or economic considerations.

ACTION PRINCIPLES TO CAPTURE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL VALUES

ODECO proposes strategies to implement in the short term to elicit the reuse of data and align it with the concept of societal values through these **Action Principles**:

1. **Support Communities of Shared Purpose and Practice**
2. **Encourage Polycentric Governance**
3. **Ensure Public Funding for Economic Sustainability**

Action principle 1: Support Communities of Shared Purpose and Practice

It is essential for local government to support the formation of new communities and already existing ones as they turn open data into real-world impacts. There are two community types: **1) Communities of shared purpose** often comprise citizens, civic groups, and local organisations united around shared goals, and **2) Communities of practice** that involve experts, practitioners, and academics who co-develop tools, standards, and solutions for societal challenges.

For example, the Gieß den Kiez (Water your Neighbourhood) project invites Berlin residents to voluntarily contribute tree-watering data through a tool built on existing OGD. This results in improved datasets for the city while engaging citizens without requiring advanced data skills, fostering a community of purpose united around local climate issues.

Communities of practice, such as the Code for Germany or Code for NL, are national networks of volunteer developers and practitioners who build tools using OGD to address local societal challenges and promote inclusive digital governance. They also share the best open data practices and provide practical solutions to the government.

Supporting both types of communities allows local governments to gather different users' infrastructure and data needs to help prioritise OGD release and projects. This also supports environmental goals and promotes citizen engagement and inclusion. Using participative design methods, communities can be created where stakeholders are involved in co-creating economic and social value out of open data locally. If supported with resources and involved in decision-making, communities of practice can provide or develop tools and standards to improve OGD delivery and use.

*Example from a similar cause:
Open Science NL has awarded
five grants to citizen science hubs
to help foster knowledge
exchange and strengthen
expertise and support for citizen
science across the Netherlands*

Action principle 2: Encourage Polycentric Governance

Engagement of the communities and other stakeholders in **collaborative decision-making** for operational decisions and collective choice-decisions in the OGD ecosystem helps promote polycentric governance. This approach emphasises the role of non-governmental, private, voluntary, and community-based actors, encouraging less centralised governance. It leverages various communities' diverse experiences, skills, and interests, enhancing open data infrastructure, reuse, and value creation.

One example of polycentric governance is *decentralised rule-making* around data reuse for AI through citizens' assemblies, resulting in the creation of a social license [iv]. Marginalised communities rarely benefit from the value their data creates. Engaging diverse and relevant stakeholders through facilitated discussions enables these communities to actively shape how their data is reused, under which specific conditions and safeguards. These engagements go beyond simple feedback, resulting in concrete governance terms.

For local governments, polycentric governance offers insight into stakeholders' needs around infrastructure or access to public services built on open data. It can also enable the feeling of collective responsibility among the municipalities, motivating them to update and maintain OGD. To support this, governments must actively engage less powerful groups in strategy development, assessments, and service design within the OGD ecosystem. Effective mechanisms include *citizens' assemblies, participatory workshops, stakeholder forums, and the facilitation of formal and informal communication networks* that promote mutual learning and collective action [v].

Action principle 3: Ensure Public Funding for Economic Sustainability

Funding for the OGD ecosystem's *infrastructure* and stakeholders is crucial for its **sustainability**. The production and use of open data depend on the infrastructure and the actors that create, control, maintain, and repair this infrastructure. A sustainable open data ecosystem attracts businesses, entrepreneurs, and investors who see economic potential in leveraging the data, and it also supports the work of existing not-for-profit actors.

Commercial users already support the sustainability of the open data ecosystem when they *rely on infrastructure* developed by others. For instance, CKAN, a data catalogue system used by both public and private entities, including the Dutch National Data Portal, was developed by the non-profit Open Knowledge Foundation. It is now under the stewardship of two private companies that, among other things, provide committed funding. This example highlights an opportunity for governments to similarly fund key projects within the open data ecosystem, particularly those that benefit less powerful groups.

Beyond public funding, context-specific strategies, i.e., **open data business models**, can be promoted to the private and third sector users. As part of the ODECO research, we looked at the case study of Esri, a significant player in the geospatial domain. Based on this analysis, we provide recommendations on the factors for the business model that would support the sustainability of the open data ecosystem [vi]. Governments can assist other actors in developing and implementing such open data business models by offering *incubator programs* that provide financial investment, training, and networking opportunities.

UNEVEN OGD VALUE DISTRIBUTION

When implementing these principles, the structural issues of uneven value distribution need to be considered. It is one of the issues that may persist in the ecosystem, and without **equitable governance structures**, existing power imbalances can be reinforced. For example, corporations or the government might prioritise their goals of profit generation or operational efficiency over broader societal benefits. This leads to **selective openness**, where only specific data is shared, benefiting the dominant users. This dynamic may *deepen existing social and economic disparities*, as the capacity to utilise open data is often tied to access to advanced tools and expertise.

GOVERNANCE SOLUTIONS TO THE OGD VALUE DISTRIBUTION CHALLENGES

To address **inherent conflicts** between different value types in the OGD ecosystem, the ODECO project's research suggests several **governance solutions**:

- **Purpose-Driven Data Initiatives:** Aligning data release and usage with societal goals, such as addressing climate change or improving healthcare, can maximise both social and economic value.
- **Governance Reform:** Transparent mechanisms for OGD sharing and accountability must be prioritised. Decentralised and participatory governance models are essential for addressing power imbalances and fostering trust among users.
- **Capacity Building:** Smaller actors, such as non-governmental organisations and local governments, require support in terms of technical expertise, infrastructure, and financial resources to engage effectively with the OGD ecosystem.
- **Innovative Incentives and Regulations:** Tax breaks, subsidies, and public-private partnerships can incentivise broader participation and redistribute the benefits of open data more equitably.

The first two governance solution suggestions of the purpose-driven data initiatives and governance reform aim to improve *the distribution of social value*. The other two solutions aim to improve or 'balance' *the distribution of economic value* in the OGD ecosystem to ensure that all actors can continue to be actively involved in it.

Purpose-Driven Data Initiatives

In a purpose-driven model, as opposed to a user-driven one, OGD initiatives are motivated by **specific social outcomes** rather than the volume of data made available. Prioritising the publication of OGD datasets in areas where there is demand for solutions will foster public trust and engagement [vii]. Additionally, if certain groups' needs are not acknowledged, data on the topic are unlikely to be collected or published, which can result in under-delivery or suboptimal delivery of public services.

Purpose-driven OGD can support existing data collaboratives that address global challenges like humanitarian aid or environmental issues. For example, non-profit organisations like Humanitarian Open Street Map provide map data necessary for disaster management via volunteer work. The government could also borrow from India's and **expand the categories of high-value datasets** to include social data about different socio-economic indicators [viii]. Another example is Belgium's creation of an independent federal public institution that fights against discrimination and promotes equality, Unia. It assessed existing resources and needs, and developed a centralised data hub, called the Equality Data Hub, of all sources of data on equality in the country [ix].

Governance Reform

For the governance reform, further enhance the existing standardised reporting system for identifying and correcting data errors on national and local OGD platforms, creating more **transparency** through the feedback loops, and improving data quality. To **address power imbalances** and **foster trust** among users, existing approaches like the 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles can be improved by referring to 'CARE' (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles. The CARE principles also focus on realising collective benefit from open datasets, as well as ensuring commitment to ethics[i]. The example of these principles being translated into the design of an open data initiative is the Open Development Mekong project.

Capacity Building

While an OGD platform already exists, more can be done to build capacity. The government should treat open data as critical social infrastructure that must be public in order to ensure the common well-being. We suggest initiating a government-wide review to restructure and streamline OGD management across agencies. Require all government agencies to use OGD in their operations, where applicable. Acknowledge that the government is not the only producer of open data. Establish **formal partnerships** with citizen-driven initiatives similar to [Zo! City](#) or [CityLab010](#) by offering funding, technical support, or official data contributions. Actively **incorporate crowdsourced data** into government planning and service delivery to share the cost of data generation and foster a collaborative ecosystem that enhances both data quality and coverage. Invest in structured **training initiatives** for public servants, civil society, journalists, and private sector actors to enhance their ability to access, interpret, and apply open data effectively to co-create value.

Innovative Incentives and Regulations

The government should implement the following measures to expand support for open data initiatives. Enact **tax policies** that offer deductions to companies and individuals who provide open data to open data initiatives. Use existing models, such as the tax-deductible status granted to donors of the Wikimedia Foundation and Open Street Map, as templates for extending similar benefits to other qualified open data organisations.

Update legal frameworks governing **public procurement** to require private contractors to publish open data, including enriched or augmented OGD, as part of their contractual obligations, to improve local governance and participation. Replicate successful examples, such as the city of Barcelona in Spain, which reclaimed its urban data through data sovereignty clauses in such contracts, requiring that the data is made available for city departments and potentially as OGD [xi].

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